

EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION TOWARDS TECH 7 AUTOMATION SYSTEMS (I) PVT LTD, COIMBATORE

Y. Kalai Selvam*, Dr. C. Gnanaprakasam & Dr. B. Velmurugan*****

* II Year MBA, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Natham, Dindigul, Tamil Nadu

** Associate Professor, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering and Technology, Natham, Dindigul, Tamil Nadu

*** Professor & Head, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering and Technology, Natham, Dindigul, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract:

Employee satisfaction and Loyalty represents one of the most key challenges faced by the managers today when it comes to managing their employees. Employees are the most valuable resource for all organizations; the longer an employee works for a company the more valuable it becomes. Many researchers have been conducted in various sectors to demonstrate the impact of Job satisfaction on employee loyalty. Employee satisfaction is all about employees being satisfied in the organization with a strong belief that working with that particular organization is their best option. The aim of the study was to find the impact of job satisfaction of an employee. This study also finds out various factors underlying employee satisfaction. To achieve the aim of the study questionnaire survey was used. The results show that there is direct impact of all the factors in the organization. Job satisfaction is related to different Socioeconomic and personal factors, such as: Age, Sex, Incentives, Working Environment, Education, duration of work etc. The present paper will highlight different factors affecting job satisfaction in pharmaceutical company in Hyderabad, India.

Key Words: Job Satisfaction, Working Conditions, Incentives, Social Security, Skill.

Introduction:

The term "Job Satisfaction" refers to an employee general attitude towards his job. Job satisfaction is how content an individual is with his or her job. The employees can be think that the organization can be fulfill their requirements such as pay, pension arrangement; working hours. It is useful to highlight its important aspects. There are three important dimensions to employee job satisfaction.

- Employee job satisfaction refers to ones feeling towards ones job. It can only be inferred but not seen
- Employee job satisfaction is often determined by how well Outcomes meet or exceed expectations satisfaction in one's job Means increased commitment in the fulfilment of formal Requirements. There is greater willingness to invest personal Energy and time in job performance
- The terms of employee job satisfaction and job attitudes are typically used interchangeably. Both refer to effective orientations On the part of individuals towards their work roles, which they are presently occupying. Positive attitude towards the job are conceptually equivalent to employee job satisfaction and negative attitudes towards the job indicate employee dissatisfaction.

Though the terms employee job satisfaction and attitudes are used interchangeably, there are difference between the two. Attitudes, as was mentioned earlier, refer to predisposition to respond. Employee job satisfaction, on the other hand, relates to performance factors. Attitudes reflect ones feeling towards individuals, organizations and objects.

Attitudes endure generally, but employee job satisfaction is dynamic, it can decline even more quickly that it developed. Managers, therefore, cannot establish the conditions leading to high satisfaction now and then neglect it, for employee satisfaction constantly.

Following are the Conditions:

- Top management actively supports the survey.
- Employees are fully involved in planning the survey.
- A clear objective exists for conducting the survey.
- The study is designed and administered consistent with standards of sound research.
- Management is capable and willing to take follow up action.
- Both the results and action plans are communicated to employees.

Ways of Measuring Employee Job Satisfaction:

There are a number of ways of measuring Employee Job Satisfaction. This is not surprising since hundreds of studies have been conducted over the past three and half decades, employing varied techniques. The most common ways of measurement include rating scales, critical incidents, interviews, and action tendencies.

Measurement of employee job satisfaction has come to acquire the same fate as the measurement of intelligence. We can measure employee job satisfaction by questionnaire. Perhaps the earliest of all the known scales of measuring employee job satisfaction is that by Hop pock (1935).

Other Effects of Employee Job Satisfaction:

In addition to the above, it has been claimed that satisfied employees tend to have better mental and physical health and learn new employee related tasks quickly.

Two Faces of Employee Job Satisfaction:

Employee job satisfaction has both functional and dysfunctional consequence. The positive consequences of employee job satisfaction have already been stated above. An often- overlooked dimension of employee job satisfaction is its relationship to employee health. Employee who are dissatisfied with their jobs are prone to managers, this means that even if satisfaction did not lead to less voluntary turnover and absence, the goal of a satisfied workforce might be justifiable because it would reduce medical or costs and the premature loss of valued employees by way of heart Disease or strokes. The effect of employee job satisfaction goes beyond organizational setting.

The employee job satisfaction helps management in terms of reduced turnover, reduced absences, reduced job stress and reduced medical and life insurance costs. Additionally, there benefits for society in general. Satisfied employees are happy and better citizens. However, employee job satisfaction has been overemphasized. Its benefits to the management are contingent upon fulfillment of several other variables. Take turnover for instance. Employee job satisfaction may not directly lead to reduced turnover, other facto like age, financial position, number of dependents and like will have their own say. It seems that only academician and researchers are interested in employee job satisfaction. For them employee job satisfaction is a good topic for survey. For them employee job satisfaction is important and they expect that it is important for others too. For many people, job is only a source for earning, nothing more, and nothing less. A dissatisfied employee has any number of off the job activities to find satisfaction. Non job oriented people tend not to be emotionally involved with their work this relative indifference allows them to accept frustrating condition at work more willingly. Unfortunately, the number of on job oriented people is more than those who take job as everything in life.

Determinants of Employee job Satisfaction:

Employee job satisfaction is critical concept to measure the employees organizational behavior. There are a number of factors influencing the employee's job satisfaction. Refers to a set of some commonly experienced stable characteristics of organizations, which constitutes the uniqueness of that organization and differentiates it from others. We face some difficulties in identifying this set of characteristic we do not yet know the various dimensions or factors of Employee job satisfaction on which we should look for these characteristic. Some of these common dimensions are described below.

Mentally Challenging Work:

Employee tent to prefer jobs that give them opportunities to use skills and abilities and offer a variety of tasks, freedom and feedback on how well they are doing are some of the most important ingredients of a satisfying job.

Working Conditions:

Employees are concerned with their work environment for personal comfort and for doing a good job. Temperature, light, noise and other environmental factors should not be extremes.

Company Policies:

If the company has policies that can help the employee on the job and of the job then the employee does his duty effectively. It provides the employee to improve the attitude of dedication and co-operation.

Job Security:

For employee the man aspects of his job are security. If the employee feels that in company here he is working then he will be satisfied and performs his duties with commitment.

Communication:

Communication includes both the transference and understanding of meaning. Good communication is essential to any group or organization effectiveness. Poor communication is probably the most frequently cited source of interpersonal conflict. An idea, no matter how great, is useless until it is transmitted and understood by others. Perfect communication, would exist when a thought or an idea was transmitted so that the mental picture perceived by the receiver was exactly the same as that envisioned by the sender.

Compensation and Rewards:

An employee reward system consists of an originations integrated policies, processes and practices for rewarding its employee in accordance with their contribution, skill and competence and their market work. It is developed within the frame work of organizations reward philosophy, strategies and policies and contains arrangement in from of processes, structures and procedures which will provide and maintain appropriate types and levels of pay, benefits and other forms rewards.

Safety and Health:

Safety, in simple terms, means freedom from the occurrence or risk of injury or loss. Industrial safety or employee safety refers to the protection of workers from the danger of the industrial accidents. An accident free plant enjoys certain benefits. Major ones are substantial savings in cost, increase productivity, moral and legal grounds. The well being of the employee in an industrial establishment is affected by accidents any by ill health physical as well as mental. The need healthy the workers and health services are to be provided by the management to ensure the continuing good health of their employees.

Rewards and Recognition:

An employee reward system consists of an origination's integrated policies, processes and practices for rewarding its employees and practices for rewarding its employees in accordance with their contribution, skill and competence and their market work. It is developed within the framework of organizations reward philosophy, strategies and contains arrangement in from of processes appropriate types and levels of pay, benefits and other forms rewards.

Career Development:

A career can define as a sequence but related work activities that provides continuity, and meaning in a person's life. Careers are both individually, perceived and society constrained; not only do people make careers out of their particular experience, but career opportunities in society also influence and make people.

Performance Appraisal:

Performance Appraisal is deemed by many to be an essential part of the executive job. A systematic and periodic appraisal process is deemed superior to a casual, intuitive, and at the absence of such preplanning. Systematic performance

appraisal is that which provides information of great assistance in making and enforcing decisions such subject as promotions, pay increases, layoffs and transfers. It provides such information in advance of time when it may be needed, they by avoiding spot judgment when a decision must be made.

Merits - Employee Job Satisfaction:

- Sets people management priorities for CEO.
- Detects potential problem areas early.
- Evaluates success of policies and practices.
- Makes employees feel involved and cared about.
- Customer and employee satisfaction are like.

Demerits - Employee Job Satisfaction:

- Managers could get lost in data.
- Inaction could destroy credibility.
- Periodic change could paralyze company.
- Employee may not reveal innermost feelings.

Statement of Problem:

It is said that satisfied workers is a productive workers any kind of grievance relating to organizational or personal to a greater extent influence on the job. So every organization is giving higher priority to keep their workers with satisfaction by providing several facilities which improve satisfaction & which reduce dissatisfaction. Employee satisfaction is considered as a key issue by the entrepreneur where efforts are taken & program are initiated. If an workers is not satisfied with the job there are chances for absenteeism, turnover, lower productivity, committing of mistakes, diverting energy for different types of conflicts keeping this thing in view all organization are trying to identify the areas where satisfaction to be improved to get out of the above dangers. In this connection a survey was conducted on behalf of Paper industries ltd to identify the level of satisfaction in terms of strongly agree to strongly disagree on various job-related factors

Objective of the Study:

Primary Objectives:

- A Study on Employee satisfaction towards Tech7 automation systems (India) Pvt. Ltd Coimbatore.

Secondary Objectives:

- The objective of the study is as follows
- To identify the factors which influence the Employee satisfaction of employees.
- To analyses the employees satisfaction with reference to working hours and leave facilities.
- To study the relationship between employees and their superiors.
- To suggest suitable remedial measures to improve the Employee satisfaction.
- To study the working environment and working hours.
- To study the safety & welfare measures provide by industry.

Need of the Study:

The study is conducted to assess the Employee satisfaction needs of the employees at tech7 automation systems (India) pvt.ltd. The study helps to know their preferences and problems of the employees. Employee commitment is essential to increase the productivity. If the Employee satisfaction increases it will increase the employee commitment, further it will lead to increase in the productivity. It is very essential to study about the Employee satisfaction

Scope of the Study:

The study is useful to find out the opinion of the workers about the Employee satisfaction. The study will predict the need of the guidance for Employee satisfaction. Through the guidance we can improve the breaks manufacturing industries. Research has given information about the Employee satisfaction prevailing in the organization

Research Design:

The research design for studying working capital management in small businesses typically involves a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitative analysis may include financial ratio analysis, trend analysis, and statistical modeling to examine the relationships between various working capital components and business performance metrics. Qualitative methods such as interviews, surveys, and case studies can provide deeper insights into the specific challenges, strategies, and decision-making processes of small business owners or managers regarding working capital management. The research design should also incorporate a suitable sampling strategy to ensure representation across different industries, sizes, and geographical locations of small businesses. Additionally, longitudinal studies may be employed to observe changes in working capital management practices over time and their impact on business outcomes.

Research Methodology:

The research methodology for studying working capital management in small businesses typically involves a multi-faceted approach that integrates both quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitative methods allow for the analysis of numerical data related to financial statements, such as balance sheets, income statements, and cash flow statements. This may include techniques like ratio analysis, trend analysis, and regression analysis to examine the relationships between working capital components and business performance metrics. Qualitative methods, on the other hand, enable researchers to gain deeper insights into the underlying reasons, motivations, and decision-making processes behind working capital management practices in small businesses. This can involve interviews, surveys, focus groups, and case studies to gather rich, contextual data from business owners, managers, and other relevant stakeholders

Analytical Tools for the Study:

- Simple percentage method

- Correlation
- Chi - square

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Satisfied with Work:

Satisfied With Your Work	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Satisfied	21	17.5
Satisfied	39	32.5
Neutral	48	40
Dissatisfied	7	5.8
Highly Dissatisfied	5	4.2
Total	120	100

Relationship with the Immediate Supervisor of the Respondents:

Relationship with the Immediate Supervisor	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Satisfied	13	10.9
Satisfied	32	26.6
Neutral	56	46.6
Dissatisfied	11	9.1
Highly Dissatisfied	8	6.8
Total	120	100

Satisfaction with the Physical Working Conditions:

Physical Working Conditions	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Satisfied	17	14.1
Satisfied	39	32.5
Neutral	44	36.6
Dissatisfied	13	10.9
Highly Dissatisfied	7	5.9
Total	120	100

Satisfaction with the Personal and Professional Skill Grow:

Personal and Professional Skill Grow	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Satisfied	32	26.6
Satisfied	26	21.6
Neutral	41	34.1
Dissatisfied	13	10.9
Highly Dissatisfied	8	6.8
Total	120	100

Satisfaction on Communication with Team:

Communication within Team	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Satisfied	37	30.9
Satisfied	41	34.1
Neutral	35	29.1
Dissatisfied	4	3.4
Highly Dissatisfied	3	2.5
Total	120	100

Satisfaction with the Current Salary of the Respondents:

Satisfied with the Current Salary	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Satisfied	26	21.8
Satisfied	29	24.1
Neutral	43	35.9
Dissatisfied	17	14.1
Highly Dissatisfied	5	4.1
Total	120	100

Suggestions:

- Focus on improving working conditions, safety measures, and providing better support systems specifically for production employees.
- Develop retention strategies such as career progression paths, employee recognition programs, and enhanced benefits for long term employees.
- Provide leadership training for supervisors to improve their management skills and foster better relationships with their teams.
- Invest in improving the physical work environment, such as ergonomic furniture, better lighting, and ensuring a clean and safe workspace.
- Implement regular and meaningful recognition programs and ensure that employee feedback is actively sought and acted upon.

- Implement better workload management practices and ensure that tasks are evenly distributed to prevent burnout.

Conclusion:

The study was conducted to find out the link between job satisfaction and the performance of employees working in private organizations. While studying the relationship of job satisfaction with different variables such as qualification, gender, occupation, family system, and marital status, it is concluded that job satisfaction has no significant association with gender, qualification, family system, as well as marital status. It is determined from the study that job satisfaction is significantly correlated with the occupation of employees. Furthermore, it is also concluded from the above results that the performance of satisfied employees is superior as compared to dissatisfied employees. Hence, the above results suggested that to improve the performance of employees such as quality of work, productivity, and leadership qualities, organizations should consider obvious factors of job satisfaction. Based on the above points we can say that employee attitudes typically reflect the morals of the company. In areas of customer service and sales, happy employees are extremely important because they represent the company to the public. So, every organization should develop strategies that strengthen the work environment and increase employee morale and employee satisfaction to enhance employee performance and productivity, which ultimately results in high profits, customer satisfaction as well as customer retention.

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